

ESG SCORES AND SHORT-TERM STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY: EVIDENCE FROM THE NIFTY 50

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the association of ESG performance with short-run stock price volatility during the period from 2019 to 2024 based on NIFTY 50 companies. The regression analysis yields a low R² value of 0.07 and statistically insignificant coefficients for environmental, social, and governance factors, showing that ESG scores have no significant impact on daily price movements. GARCH findings validate the volatility clustering in the index, especially in times of systemic shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic, but this volatility has nothing to do with ESG scores. The conclusions offer empirical evidence that ESG factors possess low short-run forecast ability within the Indian market setting, pointing towards the possibility that their function could be more significant in terms of improving long-run resilience and stability than minimizing day-to-day return volatility. These insights are important to investors, corporate managers, and policymakers for balancing sustainability considerations with market risk assessment.

Keywords: *ESG Scores, Stock Price Volatility, GARCH, NIFTY 50, Risk Assessment, Sustainable Finance*

1.Introduction

Environment, Social and Governance (ESG) scores have become increasingly crucial in assessing a company's performance in environmental, social, and governance matters. These scores serve as tools for investors and stakeholders to evaluate a company's sustainability and ethical behaviour, influencing decision-making processes in investment and corporate strategy.

Companies with high ESG scores are perceived as lower-risk investments capable of handling external challenges such as regulatory changes or reputational risks (Albuquerque et al.,2019). Research indicates that incorporating ESG factors into investment portfolios can lead to reduced risk and potential outperformance over the medium-to long-term (MSCI Research).

High ESG scores promote long-term strategic thinking, focusing on creating long-term rather than short-term gains. This approach helps companies anticipate future risks and opportunities more effectively (Khan et al.,2016).ESG scores are critical for evaluating a company's overall sustainability and ethical behaviour, impacting investor confidence, and guiding corporate strategy towards sustainable practices (Friede et al.,2015).

Studies show that companies with higher ESG scores often have higher valuation multiples, such as the EV/EBITDA multiple, indicating a positive impact on market value . Additionally, improvements in ESG scores can lead to higher valuation multiples, suggesting that the market rewards ESG performance improvements (Deloitte, 2023).

Though previous research has tended to stress ESG's contribution to firm value and risk minimization in the long term, not much is known about whether ESG performance can account for short-term emerging market volatility in India and other emerging economies. Prior research was mostly on developed markets or long-horizon returns, but it leaves a gap when it comes to understanding the salience of ESG for price movements on a daily basis. To fill this void, this research examines the extent to which ESG scores explain stock price volatility among NIFTY 50 companies from 2019 to 2024. Using regression and GARCH models, the research presents empirical findings that ESG factors have minimal explanatory power for short-run volatility in the Indian market setting. This intervention is significant in that it pushes against the assumption that ESG inherently provides upfront risk mitigation, but rather that it may be best explained by promoting long-term stability and resilience.

2.Objectives

The main aim of this study is to analyse the correlation between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) scores and stock market volatility in the NIFTY 50 index. The specific objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To examine whether ESG scores are associated with short-term stock price volatility in the NIFTY 50 index.
2. To explore differences, if any, in the volatility patterns of high- and low-ESG firms.
3. To apply econometric models such as regression and GARCH to analyse volatility dynamics in relation to ESG factors.
4. To derive insights for investors, corporates, and policymakers on the role of ESG considerations in market risk assessment and long-term stability.

3.Hypothesis-

- **H₀₁ (Null):** ESG scores do not explain variations in short-term stock price volatility among NIFTY 50 firms.
- **H₁₁ (Alternative):** ESG scores may be associated with variations in short-term stock price volatility among NIFTY 50 firms.
- **H₀₂ (Null):** There is no measurable difference in volatility between high-ESG and low-ESG firms in the NIFTY 50 index.
- **H₁₂ (Alternative):** High-ESG and low-ESG firms differ in their short-term volatility patterns in the NIFTY 50 index.

4.Literature Review

The integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors into investment analyses has garnered significant attention in recent years. This literature review synthesizes findings from various studies examining the relationship between ESG scores and stock price volatility, highlighting key insights and contributions to the field.

An increasing body of literature shows a negative relationship between high ESG scores and stock price volatility. It was examined that Chinese businesses during the COVID-19 period and discovered that more favourable ESG ratings are correlated with reduced stock price volatility, providing evidence that ESG acts as a buffer in the face of market uncertainty (Fu, 2024). This result is corroborated which show that firms with superior sustainability criteria have more favourable financial risk profiles and higher resilience during periods of high volatility (Nishant et al., 2023).

Similarly, it is pointed out that higher ESG-rated stocks tend to have lower aggregate price volatility and fewer volatility spikes, suggesting that ESG ratings can be of great use for trading and portfolio management strategies (Yegerman, 2023). This is also evidenced by a study done where it is demonstrated that firms with higher ESG scores have both higher returns and lower volatility, supporting the idea that good ESG performance makes firms more financially stable (Limkriangkrai et al., 2023).

Empirical studies on emerging markets also confirm the correlation between stock price stability and ESG scores. One such study by (Kurniawan et al., 2023) investigate the impact of ESG performance on Asian emerging market stock price volatility and conclude that companies with better ESG practices have lower volatility levels than their lower-rated peers .

This implies that the advantages of high ESG ratings are not restricted to developed markets but also apply to emerging markets.

Furthermore, an exhaustive examination discusses the connection between sustainability scores and financial performance in different industries. Their report demonstrates that companies maintaining higher sustainability practices experience less price volatility in their stocks, reinforcing the need to incorporate ESG considerations into investment choices (Maffina et al., 2022).

The implications of this study are significant for both investors and corporate planners. Investors in need of stability can opt for high-ESG shares as part of risk-mitigation strategies. The insights into the interplay between ESG ratings and stock price movements can guide investors during times of market uncertainty (Fu, 2024).

From a corporate perspective, increasing ESG compliance can lead to stable investments. Firms are incentivized to pursue sustainable behaviour not only on ethical grounds, but also for the potential to enhance financial performance in terms of lowered stock price volatility. Firms that exhibit excellent sustainability performance tend to secure long-term investors who value stability more than quick returns (Nishant et al., 2023).

The link between the ESG scores and stock price volatility has important policy implications. While governments place greater importance on sustainable development, developing frameworks that incentivize firms to enhance their ESG practices may contribute to lower market volatility as a whole. Policymakers play an important role in shaping an environment in which good ESG performance is rewarded, resulting in a more stable market (Chen & Li, 2024).

Overall, the literature shows a negative correlation between high ESG ratings and stock price volatility in different contexts. This line of research underscores the need to incorporate ESG considerations into investment research and company strategy, while offering timely insights for policymakers seeking to support sustainable economic growth (Fatemi, Glaum, & Kaiser, 2018) (Silva & Rodrigues, 2024).

5. Research Methodology

This section describes the methods used to examine the nexus between the ESG scores and day-to-day stock price volatility. The methodology was organized under three broad aspects- data collection, ESG rating classification, and statistical procedures utilized for the analysis

5.1 Data Collection

Data Source: The main data for this study are the daily closing stock prices of the NIFTY 50 index and their respective ESG ratings. The NIFTY 50 index is a stock market index that comprises the leading 50 firms listed on the National Stock Exchange of India and provides an effective picture of the Indian equity market. Daily closing price data of the NIFTY 50 index from April 2019 to March 2024 were obtained from the official National Stock Exchange of India (NSE) database.

Time period: The period analysed was from 2019 to 2024. This period provides scope for the examination of stock price volatility during various market scenarios, including the effects of special events such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Variables:

Dependent Variable: The dependent variable in this study is daily stock price return/volatility, computed on the basis of average closing prices.

Independent Variable: The independent variable is divided into ESG ratings, which are classified according to the following categories:

Adequate: Mid-range ESG scores (between the 40th and 60th percentiles).

Good: Top 30% of ESG-rated firms (above the 70th percentile).

Bad: Bottom 30% ESG-rated firms (below the 30th percentile).

5.2 Classification of ESG Ratings

The categorization of ESG ratings is important for explaining how varying degrees of ESG performance are associated with stock price behaviour. The categorization system is as follows:

Adequate: Firms that fall within the middle range of ESG scores, reflecting a balanced sustainability approach.

Good: Firms that fall in the top 30% based on their ESG scores, reflecting high commitment and performance in environmental, social, and governance aspects.

Bad: Firms with the lowest 30% of ESG rankings indicate poor sustainability performance and potential risks for their activities.

5.3 Statistical Methods:

Statistical methods were employed to analyse the relationship between ESG categories and stock price volatility.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Daily Log Returns for NIFTY 50 (2019–2024)

Year	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
2019–2020	-0.0012	0.0175	-0.1390	0.0641	-2.4955	20.1621
2020–2021	0.0023	0.0139	-0.0592	0.0840	0.2966	6.0970
2021–2022	0.0007	0.0100	-0.0490	0.0298	-0.9329	3.0942
2022–2023	-0.0001	0.0093	-0.0269	0.0285	0.0064	0.5466
2023–2024	0.0004	0.0088	-0.0611	0.0331	-0.6719	5.0702

Source: Prepared by Authors

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of daily log returns for the NIFTY 50 index from 2019 to 2024. The results reveal significant variation in volatility across the sample period. During 2019–2020, the index experienced the highest volatility (standard deviation of 0.0175) and extreme tail events (kurtosis of 20.16), which coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic crash and subsequent market turbulence. In contrast, 2020–2021 reflects a recovery phase with positive average returns (0.23%) and moderately high kurtosis (6.09), indicating the persistence of occasional large shocks despite lower volatility levels. The years 2021–2022 and 2022–2023 show more stability, with volatility declining to around 1%, although the distribution in 2021–2022 was negatively skewed, suggesting downside risk. Finally, 2023–2024 maintains relatively low volatility (0.0088) but continues to exhibit fat tails (kurtosis of 5.07), underscoring the recurrence of sharp return spikes. Overall, these findings confirm that NIFTY 50 daily returns are non-normal, leptokurtic, and subject to volatility clustering, thereby justifying the application of GARCH models for analysing volatility dynamics.

Table 2 : Descriptive Statistics of ESG Score

Statistic	E-score	S-score	G-score	Total ESG rating
Mean	34.28	47.86	54.2	63.49
Standard Error	2.79	3.26	3.68	1.21
Median	34.78	51.04	64.42	65.03
Mode	6.9	16.4	19.8	N/A
Standard Deviation	19.71	23.02	26.02	8.58
Sample Variance	388.56	529.8	677.18	73.69
Kurtosis	-0.82	-1.44	-1.66	0.68
Skewness	0.16	-0.24	-0.27	-0.79
Range	75.95	73.94	76.95	39.59
Minimum	3.3	9.4	15.3	35.41
Maximum	79.25	83.34	92.25	75
Sum	1714.22	2392.85	2709.83	3174.33
Count	50	50	50	50

Source: Prepared by Authors

Table 2 indicates that ESG ratings reveal a general improvement trend from environmental (E) to social (S) to governance (G), the highest of which is the Total ESG rating. Standard deviations in E, S, and G scores were quite high, reflecting a lot of variation within each category, with the Total ESG rating having a lower standard deviation, indicating greater consistency. Negative skewness of values for G and Total ESG implies an overweighting of scores towards the top end, perhaps pointing towards a general robustness of performance in these themes.

SUMMARY OUTPUT								
<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.27							
R Square	0.07							
Adjusted R Square	0.01							
Standard Error	36.55							
Observations	50.00							
<i>ANOVA</i>								

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	3	4708	1569.245	1.174471	0.330			
Residual	46	61462	1336.1291					
Total	49	66170						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Returns	41.56	43.94	0.95	0.35	-46.88	130.00	-46.88	130.00
E Score	0.57	0.91	0.63	0.53	-1.26	2.40	-1.26	2.40
S Score	0.04	1.03	0.04	0.97	-2.03	2.10	-2.03	2.10
G Score	-0.80	1.46	-0.55	0.59	-3.74	2.14	-3.74	2.14

Table 3: Regression Analysis between ESG Score and Average Price

Source: Prepared by Authors

Table 3 highlights that the regression test was conducted to test whether ESG scores (E, S, G) had a significant impact on NIFTY 50 index stock price volatility. The findings are as follows:

$R^2 = 0.07$: Although the model yields an R^2 of 0.07, the lack of statistical significance indicates that ESG scores provide little explanatory power for return variation.

P-values for each of the ESG dimensions (E: 0.53, S: 0.97, G: 0.59) exceed the usual threshold value (0.05), and therefore none of the predictors are statistically significant.

The Environmental Score (E) coefficient is positive (0.57) but insignificant.

The Governance Score (G) also has a negative coefficient (-0.80), but once again, it is not significant.

These findings indicate that short-term returns in the NIFTY 50 are not consistently explained by ESG ratings. The poor model fit and absence of statistical significance indicate that market sentiment, world economic trends, or company-specific news might contribute to short-run volatility much more than ESG scores.

Table 4: GARCH Model Results:

Constant Mean- GARCH Model Results:

<u>Details of Attribute and the values</u>	
Attribute	Value
R-squared	0
Adj. R-squared	0
Log-Likelihood	4844.35
AIC	-9680.7
BIC	-9659.48
No. Observations	1487
Df Residuals	1486
Df Model	1

Results of Mean Model:

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value	95% Confidence Interval
mu	7.6106e-04	8.266e-06	92.073	0.000	[7.449e-04, 7.773e-04]

Results of Volatility Model:

Parameters	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	P-value	95% Confidence Interval
Omega	2.6997e-06	2.007e-12	1.345e+06	0.000	[2.700e-06, 2.700e-06]
Alpha [1]	0.1000	2.678e-02	3.735	1.880e-04	[4.752e-02, 0.152]
Beta[1]	0.8800	1.869e-02	47.096	0.000	[0.843, 0917]

Source: Prepared by Authors

GARCH model is applied to examine whether volatility persists over time. This method helps accommodate time-varying variances in time-series data, a feature that is especially significant in financial markets where volatility tends to cluster over time.

Using this method, this study intends to conduct a detailed study on how ESG scores affect intraday stock price volatility and contribute useful findings for policymakers, analysts, and investors.

Table 4 highlights the NIFTY log returns from 2019 to 2024 which present a number of important features of the return and volatility dynamics of the market. The estimated mean daily return (μ) is around 0.076%, or an annualized return of about 19%, which signifies a persistent positive trend during the sample period. The dynamics of volatility, summarized by the GARCH coefficients, are highly persistent: the alpha (0.10) is that 10% of the previous day's shock (unanticipated return) influences current volatility, and the beta (0.88) is that 88% of yesterday's conditional volatility persists into today. Together, alpha and beta add to 0.98, an extremely high figure that implies volatility shocks die off slowly. The very small value of omega (long-run variance) indicates a steady underlying variance pattern. All of the parameters are strongly statistically significant, and the fit of the model is good, as evidenced by the large log-likelihood and small AIC. Overall, this model is representing a good capture of the clustered and persistent nature of volatility in the NIFTY index and represents a good basis for risk modelling and forecasting.

Figure 1 GARCH Model-Estimated Conditional Volatility

The Figure 1 volatility plot shows the estimated conditional volatility of NIFTY returns from 2019 to 2024. The volatility increases slightly and remains fairly stable throughout the period,

oscillating around 1% (0.01). There is, however, a sudden and notable spike around early 2020, where volatility increased to almost 6%—presumably representing the COVID-19 pandemic-created market chaos. Following this occurrence, the volatility slowly reduces and stabilizes but with occasional sudden surges thereafter, particularly early in 2022 and also briefly early in 2024. This demonstrates that although much of the volatility returned to the pre-pandemic period, there were ongoing shocks that periodically affected investor morale and market risk throughout the timeframe (Broadstock et al., 2021).

6. Discussion and Implications

The findings of this research give empirical support that ESG performance does not have a significant effect on short-term stock price volatility in NIFTY 50 companies. The regression results provided weak explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.07$) and statistically insignificant coefficients for environmental, social, and governance aspects, meaning that day-to-day return variability is more influenced by market-wide shocks and firm-specific causes than by sustainability scores. The GARCH findings also identify the persistence of volatility clustering, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, but not in a manner related to ESG performance. This finding concurs with the perception that ESG benefits might appear in the form of long-term resilience and risk management, but not as predictors of short-run price behaviour.

Analysis of the correlation between ESG scores and day-to-day stock price movements has yielded findings of central concern to investors, corporate management, and policymakers. Our study finds limited short-term evidence linking ESG performance to stability, which aligns with prior research suggesting ESG may be more relevant in the long run .

Our findings diverge from many prior studies (e.g., Fu, 2024; Nishant et al., 2023), which may reflect differences in market maturity, time horizon, or ESG data quality in India.

Investor Perspective: ESG as a Stability Indicator

Although prior research has suggested higher stability in high-ESG stocks, our results do not find statistically significant evidence of such stability in the short run for the Indian market. Although prior studies suggest high-ESG firms may display more stability, our regression results do not show statistically significant evidence of such an effect in the Indian short-term context. (Berg et al., 2022).

From a corporate strategy perspective, the implications are also important. Firms that are eager to attract stable investments need to be interested in improving their ESG compliance. Those

that explicitly emphasize environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and ethical management are likely to attract investment from investors seeking long-term value creation. While our results show no significant short-term impact, prior evidence suggests that ESG may contribute to long-term investment stability and value creation. Companies must thoroughly embed ESG principles into their business operations and decision-making processes, ensuring that sustainability is an integral part of their long-term strategy. Transparency and disclosure of ESG performance are equally important, as clear communication builds trust and strengthens investor confidence. Since ESG is a dynamic process, firms must pursue continuous improvement in their practices to remain attractive to investors and maintain credibility. Our evidence suggests ESG may not materially influence short-term volatility, but could matter more for long-run resilience and market stability. While our short-term results show no significant effect, prior research indicates ESG regulations may diminish volatility in the long run, a point that warrants further study in the Indian context. If strong ESG standards can facilitate greater stability in stock prices, regulatory regimes that encourage or require ESG adherence may have macroeconomic benefits. By encouraging more responsible corporate practices, these regulations could create more stable market behaviour, which is good for both investors and the economy as a whole (Dhingra & Mittal 2021).

Policymakers should work toward the standardization of ESG metrics by creating and implementing uniform reporting frameworks that ensure consistency and comparability across companies. To encourage greater adoption, governments can introduce incentives such as tax benefits or privileged access to capital for firms that actively enhance their ESG performance. At the same time, strong regulatory supervision is essential, with regulators monitoring and enforcing ESG rules so that businesses remain accountable for their environmental, social, and governance practices. Ultimately, our evidence suggests that ESG may have more material effects on long-term stability rather than short-term stock market performance. Through acknowledgment and action of these consequences, investors, companies, and policymakers can unlock the potential of ESG in building a sustainable, secure, and richer world.

7.Limitations

There are a few limitations to this study that need to be addressed. First, the analysis is performed only on the NIFTY 50 index, thereby limiting its relevance to large markets. The dataset should be larger and include mid- and small-cap stocks to gain more insight into the relationship between ESG scores and stock volatility. Second, the research itself is centered

primarily on day-to-day returns, which may not entirely reflect the long-term impact of ESG factors on financial performance. ESG-driven market reactions are typically realized over very long-time frames, and short-term volatility may not reflect the true risk or returns associated with sustainable business practices. Third, the regression model used here has low explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.07$), suggesting that macroeconomic, geopolitical, and market sentiment drivers other than those used in this study may be more significant in explaining stock price changes. The lack of statistically significant correlations between ESG ratings and volatility also implies that other factors such as liquidity, firm size, and industry-specific risks must be incorporated into future models. The study also fails to account for external shocks such as financial crises or regulatory changes, which affect both ESG adoption and stock performance. The analysis is constrained by a relatively small sample size, which may limit the statistical power of the regression results and restrict the generalizability of the findings. Finally, the application of historical ESG scores assumes uniformity in ESG measurement and reporting guidelines, but variations in ESG rating models across agencies may introduce inconsistencies in the data. Addressing these limitations in future research will enhance the validity of ESG-volatility studies and provide more informative insights for policymakers and investors.

8. Conclusion

This research aimed to analyse whether the ESG scores impact short-term stock price volatility among NIFTY 50 companies from 2019 to 2024. The results present empirical evidence that the daily return variability is not strongly influenced by ESG performance, as evidenced through the low explanatory ability of the regression model and the insignificant coefficients across all ESG dimensions. Although GARCH analysis verifies the volatility clustering in the Indian market, especially during system shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic, these trends had nothing to do with ESG factors. These findings imply that the value of ESG might be less about alleviating short-term volatility and more about contributing to long-term resilience in the market and investor confidence.

This study examined whether ESG scores influence daily stock price volatility in the NIFTY 50 index. The evidence suggests that ESG factors do not significantly predict short-term price movements. The regression model demonstrated weak explanatory power, and none of the ESG dimensions were statistically significant. Although volatility clustering was evident in the GARCH model, it was unrelated to ESG performance.

Overall, these results highlight that ESG should not be used in isolation as a predictor of short-run market risk. Instead, ESG considerations may provide greater value in long-term investment strategies, particularly when combined with macroeconomic and financial indicators. Future research should extend this analysis beyond the NIFTY 50, test different markets and industries, and explore ESG's effect on risk-adjusted returns over longer horizons.

9.Future Research Directions

Given the limitations of this study, several areas for future research can enhance our understanding of ESG's impact on stock price volatility.

Extending the study outside NIFTY 50 by incorporating global stock indices such as the S&P 500, FTSE 100, or MSCI ESG indexes can provide more insight into ESG's interrelation with volatility. A comparison of developed and emerging markets can reveal whether ESG's effect on volatility varies with economic development. Incorporating machine learning models (such as Random Forest, XGBoost, or LSTM neural networks) may improve volatility forecasting using ESG scores. The GARCH model can be utilized to test time-varying volatility and determine whether ESG factors are responsible for clustering volatility over time. Examining whether the impact of ESG scores differs across industries, such as technology, finance, or manufacturing, can provide industry-specific insights. Certain industries (e.g., energy and mining) can be subject to more ESG-related volatility impacts owing to environmental concerns and regulatory risks.

The long-term impact of ESG scores on risk-adjusted returns, rather than daily returns, may provide a better indication of ESG's financial significance. Conducting an event study analysis around material ESG-related announcements or regulatory changes can reveal how markets react to such events. Future studies must examine how investors incorporate ESG into portfolio risk management planning, and whether regulatory policies support stable ESG investments. To determine whether institutional investors (e.g., sovereign wealth funds and pension funds) react differently to ESG-driven volatility than retail investors.

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